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CONNECTIVISM AND PDCA: AN INTEGRATED APPROACH TO EDUCATIONAL INNOVATION

AUTHORS

Adilson Sousa da Silva: PhD candidate in Educational Sciences at the Universidad de La Integración de Las Américas – PY, Professor of Science and Biology, and Coordinator of Educational Management at the State Secretariat of Education and School Sports of Amazonas.

Contact: prof.adilson14@gmail.com | +55(92)99164-8902

Ana Lúcia de Castro Magalhães: Master's student in Educational Sciences at the Universidad de La Integración de Las Américas – PY, Teacher in the municipal public school system (Early Years) at the Municipal Education Departments of Mariana and Ouro Preto – Minas Gerais, Brazil.

Contact: alcmaga@hotmail.com | +55(31)98532-8797

ABSTRACT

This study investigates the combination of connectivism and the PDCA cycle for optimization in the digital age of school management. The PDCA cycle, also called the Deming Cycle, is a powerful tool used for continuous process improvement, while connectivism is a theory based on the interconnection of people through knowledge and information networks. The integration of these approaches allows educational institutions to create more efficient learning environments. This work discusses how the combined application of these two theories can transform school management, addressing challenges such as resistance to change and the need for innovation in pedagogy. Furthermore, strategies for implementing continuous improvements and overcoming challenges are analyzed. The results indicate that more effective management, with optimized processes and greater involvement of all members of the school community, promotes an environment that better meets the demands of the digital society.

Keywords: Connectivism. PDCA Cycle. School Management.